

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV)

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Abstract : Some new and novel complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV) of the type [(sb)SnCl_{n-2}(sb')] [where sb = Schiff bases; salicylidene-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene (*p-smabH*), salicylidene-3-nitro-1-amino benzene (*snabH*); sb' = Schiff bases; 4-nitrobenzylidene-2-aminophenol (*nbaphH*), salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (*sapH*), salicylidene-4-aminoacetophenone (*saapheH*) and n = 2 for tin(II), 4 for tin(IV)] have been prepared by the interaction of metal chloride with sodium salts of Schiff bases in the presence of benzene-methanol mixture. All these complexes are monomeric in nature. The complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV) are coloured solids with sharp melting points and were characterized on the basis of elemental (C, H, N, Cl and Sn) analysis and spectral [IR, NMR (¹H, ¹³C) and FAB-mass] studies.

Keywords : Tin(II) and tin(IV), Schiff bases, NMR, FAB-mass.

Introduction

A careful survey of the literature revealed that there is considerable scope for systematic investigations on the synthesis and biochemical applications of the complexes of non-transition elements particularly of tin with biologically active Schiff bases¹⁻⁴. Schiff bases and their metal complexes exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activity which includes bactericidal⁵, fungicidal⁶ and acaricides⁷. The potential role that Schiff base complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV) may play in preclinical screening of new anti-tumour⁸ agents has been the driving force behind many workers in the study of tin(II) and tin(IV) complexes of Schiff bases. Subsequently many Schiff base complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV) have been synthesized and characterized for possible use in preclinical applications. These observations prompted us to undertake the synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV) of the type [(sb)Sn_{n-2}(sb')] with the view that the newly synthesized complexes may find use as bioactive materials.

Results and discussion

The Schiff base complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV) of the type [(sb)Sn_{n-2}(sb')] have been synthesized by the interaction of methanolic solution of anhydrous metal chloride with methanolic solution of sodium salts of Schiff

bases in 1 : 1 molar ratio which can be represented by the following chemical equation :

[where sb = *p-smabH*, *snabH*

n = 2 for tin(II) {1-6} and 4 for tin(IV) {7-12}]

These complexes on treating with methanolic solution of sodium salts of Schiff bases in 1 : 1 molar ratio afford complexes of the type [(sb)SnCl_{n-2}(sb')] which can be illustrated by the following chemical equation :

(where sb' = *nbaphH*, *sapH*, *saapheH*)

All these complexes are coloured solids and were found to be soluble in common organic solvents. The details are given in Table 1.

The infrared spectra (Table 2) of Schiff bases showed the absorption bands in the region 1638–1612 cm⁻¹ due to the stretch vibration of C=N group which get shifted to lower frequency region in the complexes and observed at 1615–1585 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination via azomethine group⁹. In the complexes the absence of band in the re-

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of tin(II) and tin(IV) complexes

Sl. no.	Complexes	Yield (%)	Physical state	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
					Sn	Cl	C	H	N
1.	[(<i>p</i> -smab)Sn(saaphe)] 1	83	Light orange solid	140	20.78 (20.93)	-	61.42 (61.35)	4.15 (4.23)	4.78 (4.94)
2.	[(<i>p</i> -smab)Sn(nbaph)] 2	77	Light yellow solid	> 320 ^a	20.68 (20.82)	-	56.71 (56.83)	3.56 (3.70)	7.21 (7.37)
3.	[(<i>p</i> -smab)Sn(sap)] 3	81	Yellow solid	172	22.29 (22.43)	-	59.14 (59.32)	3.87 (3.99)	7.91 (7.98)
4.	[(snab)Sn(saaphe)] 4	69	Dark brown solid	245 ^b	19.92 (19.84)	-	55.95 (56.17)	3.42 (3.51)	7.15 (7.02)
5.	[(snab)Sn(nbaph)] 5	75	Reddish brown solid	195 ^b	19.58 (19.74)	-	56.76 (51.90)	2.93 (3.00)	9.22 (9.32)
6.	[(snab)Sn(sap)] 6	77	Yellowish orange solid	169	21.16 (21.30)	-	53.77 (53.86)	3.11 (3.23)	10.17 (10.05)
7.	[(<i>p</i> -smab)SnCl ₂ (saaphe)] 7	75	Brown solid	195	18.48 (18.60)	11.06 (11.13)	54.19 (54.54)	3.62 (3.76)	4.25 (4.39)
8.	[(<i>p</i> -smab)SnCl ₂ (nbaph)] 8	73	Light brown solid	228	18.47 (18.52)	11.05 (11.08)	50.65 (50.54)	3.21 (3.28)	6.49 (6.55)
9.	[(<i>p</i> -smab)SnCl ₂ (sap)] 9	82	Light brown solid	210	19.81 (19.88)	11.78 (11.89)	52.04 (52.26)	3.44 (3.52)	6.90 (7.03)
10.	[(snab)SnCl ₂ (saaphe)] 10	87	Dirty green solid	175	17.67 (17.74)	10.58 (10.61)	50.08 (50.22)	3.06 (3.14)	6.15 (6.28)
11.	[(snab)SnCl ₂ (nbaph)] 11	82	Light brown solid	180	17.58 (17.66)	10.53 (10.57)	46.35 (46.43)	2.61 (2.68)	8.38 (8.33)
12.	[(snab)SnCl ₂ (sap)] 12	86	Light brown solid	190	18.87 (18.90)	11.22 (11.31)	45.77 (45.86)	2.79 (2.87)	8.85 (8.92)

^aNeither melt nor decomposed, ^bdecomposed.

gion 3485–3352 cm⁻¹ suggest the deprotonation of phenolic OH on complexation¹⁰. The presence of characteristic ν_{C-O} (phenolic) bands in 1299–1276 cm⁻¹ region confirm the bonding of ligands to metal through phenolic oxygen¹¹. In the complexes (**3**, **6**, **9**, **12**) the simultaneous bonding of phenolic oxygen, azomethine and ring nitrogen with the same tin atom is ruled out due to the steric reasons and consequently no coordination was appeared between the ring nitrogen and tin atom¹². The infrared spectrum of the ligand saapheH exhibited an intense band at about 1685–1695 cm⁻¹ attributed to the ν_{C=O} stretching mode which remains almost unchanged in the spectra of the complexes (**1**, **4**, **7**, **10**). These observations are indicative of non-participation of *para* C=O group¹³.

The bands observed in the range 559–533 cm⁻¹ and 483–449 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the vibration associated with the Sn–O and Sn–N stretching frequency respectively¹⁴. In the tin(IV) complexes (**7**, **12**) the bands ob-

served in the region 330–320 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to ν_{Sn-Cl} stretching modes as terminal chlorine¹⁵. There is no evidence of bridging in the IR spectra as bands are not observed in the lower region. This fact has been further supported by FAB-mass spectral studies as complexes showed monomeric nature.

The complexes exhibited signals in the region δ 9.40–8.60 ppm (Table 3) because of deshielding on complex formation which suggest the involvement of azomethine nitrogen¹⁶ in coordination. In the complexes the absence of any signal due to phenolic proton (-OH) known to occur at δ 12.80–12.40 ppm further support the IR spectral observations. The chemical shift reported for the aromatic hydrogens in the region δ 7.90–6.08 ppm have been observed to resonate at lower field in the complexes¹⁷. In the ¹H NMR spectra of the Schiff base, saapheH additional signals are observed in the region δ 1.96–1.56 ppm due to the *p*-COCH₃ protons which shifted to higher field due to shielding¹⁸ in the corresponding complexes

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) of tin(II) and tin(IV) complexes

Complexes	$\nu_{\text{Sn-Cl}}$	$\nu_{\text{Sn-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Sn-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic)	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{NO}_2(\text{as})}$, $\nu_{\text{NO}_2(\text{sy})}$
1	–	472	535	1280	1597	–
2	–	468	549	1299	1590	1405(as), 1341(sy)
3	–	451	542	1276	1611	–
4	–	483	533	1282	1592	1409(as), 1349(sy)
5	–	464	543	1278	1589	1387(as), 1336(sy)
6	–	455	541	1285	1599	1419(as), 1375(sy)
7	330	474	534	1281	1615	–
8	329	465	554	1277	1587	1411(as), 1357(sy)
9	322	453	546	1276	1606	–
10	329	478	535	1288	1585	1419(as), 1337(sy)
11	320	463	559	1276	1596	1410(as), 1346(sy)
12	325	449	547	1298	1603	1416(as), 1371(sy)

(1, 4, 7, 10). The signals due to other protons and their shifts in the corresponding complexes are congruous with proposed structure.

¹³C NMR spectra : The nature of the complexes discussed so far was further supported by the ¹³C NMR spectra (Table 3). The presence of signals in the range δ 157.45–151.28 ppm indicate the coordination of azomethine nitrogen¹⁹. The signals appeared in the range δ 160.54–158.76 ppm suggest the coordination of phenolic oxygen via metal oxygen bond formation¹⁹. The ligand saapheH exhibited a sharp signal at around δ 190.24 ppm²⁰ due to the carbon of C=O group which remains unchanged on complexation (1, 4, 7, 10). The observed fact suggest the non-involvement of C=O group on com-

plexation.

FAB-mass spectra : The FAB-mass spectrum of the complex [(*p*-smab)SnCl₂(saaphe)] (7) exhibited the molecular ion (M⁺) peak at *m/z* 638 suggesting the monomeric nature of the complex. Other important peaks observed at *m/z* 567, 547, 428, 409, 357, 329, 238, 189, 154 and 118 are correspond to the fragmented species (Scheme 1) after the successive removal of different groups.

Experimental

Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture during experimental manipulations. All reagents were of GR or AnalaR grade. Anhydrous SnCl₄ (Loba) was dis-

Table 3. NMR (¹H and ¹³C) chemical shifts (δ , ppm) of tin(II) and tin(IV) complexes

Complexes	¹ H NMR			¹³ C NMR			
	HC=N	Aromatic protons	COCH ₃	C=N	C=O (phenole)	COCH ₃	Aromatic carbons
1	9.17	7.90–7.35	1.67	155.11	158.88	190.22	141.17, 126.26, 123.46
2	9.40	6.39–6.71	–	151.96	159.67	–	141.53, 125.86, 122.58
3	9.08	7.15–6.97	–	153.83	160.11	–	142.09, 124.68, 123.57
4	9.21	7.25–7.03	1.62	154.12	158.76	191.24	141.58, 125.66, 121.84
5	9.30	6.98–6.47	–	156.08	159.14	–	140.98, 124.76, 123.12
6	8.81	7.32–7.02	–	152.55	159.66	–	140.27, 126.05, 121.78
7	9.15	7.78–7.19	1.72	153.58	159.10	190.34	141.88, 125.98, 122.09
8	8.60	6.57–6.08	–	157.45	160.06	–	141.79, 126.11, 121.89
9	8.79	7.11–6.90	–	156.30	159.19	–	141.11, 125.87, 123.10
10	9.11	7.18–6.84	1.69	153.80	158.87	190.25	140.79, 124.87, 122.34
11	9.33	6.88–6.35	–	151.28	160.54	–	142.02, 126.10, 122.95
12	9.10	7.08–6.86	–	156.93	158.92	–	140.70, 126.08, 122.76

Scheme 1. Mass fragmentation pattern of tin(IV) complex $[(p\text{-smab})\text{SnCl}_2(\text{saaphe})]$ (7) showing composition and structure.

tilled prior to usage whereas hydrated metal chloride ($\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Loba) was made anhydrous before use by treating it with acetic anhydride. Ligands were synthesized by previous established literature methods²¹⁻²³ by using salicylaldehyde, *m*-nitroaniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, 2-aminopyridine and 4-aminoacetophenone. Tin was estimated gravimetrically as SnO_2 whereas estimation of chlorine was done by Volhard's method. Elemental analyses were carried out by RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow. IR spectra were recorded as nujol mulls using Perkin-Elmer 1000 FTIR spectrometer. NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6/\text{CDCl}_3$ on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer. The FAB-mass spectra were recorded on Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer using argon/xenon as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})]$: To a methanolic solution ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) of anhydrous tin(II) chloride (0.256 g, 1.35 mmol) was added dropwise the requisite amount of sodium salt of salicylidene-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene (0.315 g, 1.35 mmol) in methanol ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for $\sim 4 \text{ h}$, during which the colour of the solution was changed from light yellow to yellow. The precipitate of sodium chloride (0.079 g, 1.35 mmol) so formed was filtered off when $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})]$ was obtained as a yellow solid. The product so obtained was purified by recrystallisation from benzene-methanol mixture to afford yellow powdered solid (0.398 g, 81%). Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of complex $[(\text{snab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})]$.

Reaction of $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})]$ with $\text{Na}(\text{saaphe})$: A methanolic solution ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) of sodium salt of salicylidene-4-amino acetophenone (0.358 g, 1.37 mmol) was added to a methanolic solution ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) of monochloro (salicylidene-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene) (0.499 g, 1.37 mmol) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for $\sim 4 \text{ h}$, during which the colour of the solution was changed from light yellow to orange. The precipitated sodium chloride (0.08 g, 1.37 mmol) was removed by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated by distillation and dried under reduced pressure to afford light orange solid $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{saaphe})]$ (1). The product was recrystallised from benzene-methanol mixture to give light orange crystalline solid (0.645 g, 83%).

Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{nbaph})]$ (2), $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{sap})]$ (3), $[(\text{snab})\text{Sn}(\text{saaphe})]$ (4), $[(\text{snab})\text{Sn}(\text{nbaph})]$ (5) and $[(\text{snab})\text{Sn}(\text{sap})]$ (6).

The physical and analytical details are given in Table 1.

Synthesis of $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})_3]$: To a methanolic solution ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) of sodium salt of (salicylidene-4-methyl-1-amino benzene) (0.271 g, 1.61 mmol) was added tin tetrachloride (0.303 g, 1.61 mmol) with constant stirring and it was refluxed for $\sim 3 \text{ h}$, during which the colour of the solution changed from light yellow to yellow. The precipitated sodium chloride (0.068 g, 1.16 mmol) was removed by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated and dried *in vacuo* to afford yellow solid $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})_3]$ which was purified by recrystallisation from benzene-methanol mixture to produce yellow crystalline solid (0.399 g, 79%).

The complex $[(\text{snab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})_3]$ was prepared by the similar procedure.

Reaction of $[(p\text{-smab})\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})_3]$ with $\text{Na}(\text{saaphe})$: Methanolic solution ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$) of sodium salt of salicylidene-4-amino acetophenone (0.313 g, 1.20 mmol)

Fig. 1. Proposed structures of tin(II) and tin(IV) complexes.

was added with constant stirring to a methanolic solution of trichloro(salicylidene-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene)tin(IV) (0.522 g, 1.20 mmol) and was allowed to reflux for ~4 h, during which time the colour of solution was changed from yellow to brown. The precipitated sodium chloride (0.07 g, 1.20 mmol) was removed by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated and dried *in vacuo* to give dirty brown solid [(*p*-smab)SnCl₂(saaphe)] (7) which was purified by recrystallisation from benzene-methanol mixture to afford dirty brown powdered solid (0.574 g, 75%).

Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of [(*p*-smab)SnCl₂(saaphe)](8), [(*p*-smab)SnCl₂(sap)] (9), [(snab)SnCl₂(saaphe)] (10), [(snab)SnCl₂(nbaph)] (11) and [(*p*-mab)SnCl₂(sap)] (12). The physical and analytical data are collected in Table 1.

Based upon the analytical and spectral data tetrahedral geometry for tin(II) and octahedral geometry around tin(IV) in these complexes is proposed (Fig. 1).

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